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Effect of Values Clarification Counselling Technique on Aggressive Behaviour among Senior Secondary School Students in Kontagora Metropolis, Niger State

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Abstract

This study examined the effect of values clarification counselling techniques on aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora metropolis, Niger State. Pretest posttest quasi experimental research design was adopted. The target population for the study consists of senior secondary school students. A sample size of 15 participants was purposively selected from senior secondary school two students for the study consisting of 11 males and 4 females. An instrument titled Students Aggressive Behaviour Questionnaire (SABQ) was used to obtain data for both pre and posttest. The intervention sessions lasted for ten weeks (two sessions of 60 minutes each per week) during the third term 2021/2022 academic session. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistical tools of mean, standard deviation and inferential statistical tools of paired sample t-test. The findings revealed that values clarification counselling technique had a significant effect on hostile, emotional and relational aggressive behaviour among students with $t=11.00$, $p=.000$; $t=6.15$, $p=.000$ and $t=7.54$, $p=.000$ respectively. It was concluded that values clarification counselling technique was effective in reducing aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students. It was therefore recommended among others that, school counsellors and psychologists should employ values clarification counselling techniques in reducing aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students.

Keywords: Aggression, Values, Values Clarification, Secondary School Students

Introduction

Aggressive behaviour is one of the universal evils seen among students and its pervasiveness among secondary school students is worrying. Aggressive behaviours are behaviours aimed at causing harm to person or animals. They are expressed by students in different forms which could be categorized into hostile, instrumental, relational or emotional. Hostility behaviour is exhibited to cause pain to someone who made one angry or feel uncomfortable. Emotional aggression is harm caused impulsively to other person such as fan of a rival school in a sport competition. The instrumental aggressive behaviour is expressed to cause displeasure to others to achieve a non-aggressive goal such as attention, recognition and social approval. Relational aggression is causing displeasure to the relatives and friends of and things belonging to others. Aggressive behaviour such as assault, stabbing, violence and riot is seen in both male and female, though variation exists both in types and reasons for which it is exhibited. Manifestations of aggressive behaviours are common among secondary school students and it is a persistent security challenge in Kontagora. The pervading incidence of aggressive behaviour among secondary school students

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is one of the most frustrating issues confronting parents, teachers, school administration and community leaders. According to Effiom, et al., (2022), unfriendly parent's behaviour, authoritative and dishonest behaviour of teachers, poor teacher-students interaction, pressure of studies, unfriendly relationship with peers and societal injustice are the causes of aggressive behaviour among students.

From a national survey of crime and safety in Nigeria, it was revealed that aggressive behaviour is on the increase (Cleen Foundation, 2012 in Jimoh, Sambo, Bello & Dagari 2022). Data from Anambra State Ministry of Education between 2012 and 2013 showed that a total of 6,580 (68%) secondary school students were involved in 2,996 violence cases in 257 public secondary schools (Obikeze & Obi, 2015). According to Obikeze & Obi (2015), adolescent in secondary schools frequently manifest aggressive behaviour such as arson, bullying, beating, hitting and knife attack. They stated further that the cause of aggression among adolescents include television viewing, stressful situation, and use of internet. Aggressive behaviours are expressed by students in various forms which could be categorized into hostile, instrumental, relational or emotional. Hostile aggressive behaviour is exhibited to cause discomfort to someone who made one angry or feel uncomfortable; it is motivated by a desire to hurt a person. Hostile aggression could be by hitting, kicking or blowing. Emotional aggression is harm caused impetuously to other person such as fan of a rival school in a sport competition. In emotional aggression, harm is often impulsive and it is carried out at the heat of the moment. The instrumental aggressive behaviour is exhibited to cause displeasure to others to achieve non aggressive goals such as attention, recognition and social approval, money, social status and sex. The harm caused by instrumental aggression to the victim is simply a means of attaining other desired goals. This could be for personal reasons such as seeking attention, power or even self-defense. Shouting at another student in order to gain attention, turning the hand of a fellow student just to use his pen and stealing are examples of instrumental aggression. Relational aggression is causing displeasure to another person's relatives, friends and things. It also involves causing harm by damaging the reputation of another person. This is done through spreading hateful rumour, lies, rejection and excluding another person from group activity.

Manifestation of aggressive behaviours among students has a lot of consequences; the aggressive students are often socially rejected and stigmatized, lost opportunity to participate in class activities, interrupt the teaching and learning process, challenge the teachers and may cause poor concentration. Aggressive behaviour could also increase truancy and drop out among students who are victims of aggression and may increase the rate of violence in schools (Jimoh, Sambo, Bello & Dagari 2022).

One of the contributing factors to the development of aggressive behaviour among students is misunderstanding of their values. Senior secondary school students are mostly adolescent troubled with decisions making concerning their attitude and action in response to school, home, religion, love, sex and friendship needs. To make decisions at this stage of development requires clear values and focus. Values clarification is a counselling approach that focuses on assisting people to choose a direction, make a decision, and identify their priorities in reaching an objective (Kirschenbaum, 2013). Values clarification counselling provides learning experiences which help individuals to reflect their actions and reactions about life. Murad (2014) stated that values clarification is also a means of reflecting, examining and recollection about our lives in order to discover within ourselves clearly what we like and dislike. Value clarification counselling raises issues concerning students' values; make them sort out their values rather than forcing them to accept a particular value. It helps students become conscious of their values and how their values influence their actions, reaction and decisions, thus determine their ways of lives. Students can be more self-directed and effective when they understand their values better.

The process of value clarification is more than an educational experience. It is not a didactic process using a teacher to explain to the client what is good and acceptable rather it is helping learner to be more aware and clarify his values. This could help students look inward and reflect on some life confusing situations with the hope of living in a less confused world. Empirical evidence attested to the effectiveness of value clarification technique on punctuality problem (Rai, 2014) and dropout tendency (Oliha & Adu, 2015). Based on this background the researcher investigated the effect of value clarification counselling technique on aggressive behaviour of senior secondary school students in Kontagora Metropolis, Nigeria.

The incidence and prevalence of aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students are seen in rioting, fighting with weapons such as knives, sticks, bottle and cutlasses. These are used among students for fighting especially during evening games, inter class/inter-house or inter-school competitions which leave many students with injuries and emotional trauma. Bullying, biting, shoving, pushing, slapping, spreading of false rumour and names calling are also means of exhibiting aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students. This has negative impacts on the academics of the students and their overall wellbeing in the school. The adverse effect of aggression among students does not only affect the academic performance but also messed up the normal functioning of the school system. It also has a great implication on aggressive

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victims and families. Despite measures such as corporal punishment, suspension and expulsion given by schools, aggressive behaviour is still rampant among senior secondary school students in Kontagora. Therefore, there is the need for empirical studies to unveil strategies that would help in reducing aggressive behaviour most especially in schools. This study investigated the effect of value clarification counselling techniques on aggressive behaviours among senior secondary school students in Kontagora metropolis, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study are to determine the effect of:

1. Values clarification counselling technique on hostile aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora Metropolis, Niger State, Nigeria.
2. Values clarification counselling technique on emotional aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora Metropolis, Niger State, Nigeria.
3. Values clarification counselling technique on instrumental aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora Metropolis, Niger State, Nigeria.
4. Values clarification counselling technique on relational aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora Metropolis, Niger State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The study seeks to find answers to the following research questions:

1. What is the effect of values clarification counselling technique on hostile aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora Metropolis?
2. What is the effect of values clarification counselling technique on emotional aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora Metropolis?
3. What is the effect of values clarification counselling technique on instrumental aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora Metropolis?
4. What is the effect of values clarification counselling technique on relational aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora Metropolis?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses are formulated to guide the study:

1. There is no significant difference between values clarification counselling technique and hostile aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora Metropolis.
2. There is no significant difference between values clarification counselling technique and emotional aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora Metropolis.
3. There is no significant difference between value values clarification counselling and instrumental aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora Metropolis.
4. There is no significant difference between values clarification counselling technique and relational aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora Metropolis.

Methodology

The research design adopted was quasi-experimental pre-test post-test design without control group. The adoption of this design provides the benefit of comparing the pre-test and post-test results in order to analyze the effect of the treatment. The population for the study comprises all senior secondary school two students in Kontagora metropolis. There were approximately 1,988 senior secondary school two students in Kontagora metropolis (Niger State Ministry of Education, 2022). There were 51 senior secondary school two students who were identified with the characteristic of aggression in Kontagora Metropolis, Niger State, Nigeria. Fifteen (15) senior secondary school two students were purposively selected for the study. The choice of fifteen participants is premised on the submission of Jimoh, Ezembu and Abdulkadir (2016) and American Psychology Association (2019) that group counselling is among clients not more than fifteen. Students Aggressive Behaviour Questionnaire (SABQ) was used to obtain data for both pre and post-test.

To measure contents validity of the instruments (Student Aggressive Behaviour Questionnaire), the instruments was given to the experts in the Department of Educational Psychology and Counselling, test and measurement for validation. Test-retest method of reliability was used for determining the reliability of the instrument. It was administered on the same group of

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thirty (30) respondents at an interval of four weeks. The two sets of scores were correlated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient statistical tool. The coefficient of 0.82 was obtained; this showed that SBQ is reliable and adequate for this study. An introductory letter was written to the department of secondary education board, Ministry of Education, Minna, Niger state from which the introductory letter to the principal of the sample secondary school was obtained. The researchers sampled students with aggressive behaviours and administered the instrument to them. The filled questionnaire was scored and these scores form their pre-test. After the pre-test, the researchers administered the value clarification counselling treatment on the participants. The treatment took ten weeks (two sessions per week) during the third term 2021/2022 academic session. The strategies of values voting and public interview were used in values clarification for aggressive behaviour in this study. After the treatment, the researchers re-administered the Students Behaviour Questionnaire (SBQ) on the participants. The scores obtained constitute the post-test scores for the study. The descriptive statistics of means and standard deviation were adopted in answering the research questions while inferential statistical tools of Paired sample t-test was used to test the hypotheses.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the effect of values clarification counselling technique on hostile behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora Metropolis?

Table 1: Result of Descriptive Statistic of Mean, Standard Deviation on the Effect VC Counselling Technique on Hostility Aggressive Behaviour among Secondary School Kontagora Metropolis

Treatment	Variables	N	Mean	SD
VCCT	Pre-Test	15	52.73	5.89
	Post-Test	15	24.13	7.75

Result in table 1 showed that the subjects pre-test mean score is 52.73 and post-test mean score is 24.13. This means that the post-test have a mean reduction of 28.60 from the pre-test. This suggests that values clarification counselling technique may have effect on the hostility aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora metropolis.

Research Question 2

What is the effect of values clarification counselling technique on emotional aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora Metropolis?

Table 2: Result of Descriptive Statistic of Mean, Standard Deviation on the Effect VC Counselling Technique on Emotional Aggressive Behaviour among Secondary School Kontagora Metropolis

Treatment	Variables	N	Mean	SD
VCCT	Pre-Test	15	31.07	5.31
	Post-Test	15	16.20	7.56

From the result in table 2, it is revealed that the subjects exposed to values clarification counselling technique had a pre-test mean score of 31.07 and post-test mean score of 16.20, which indicates that the post-test have a mean reduction of 14.87 from the pre-test. This suggests that values clarification counselling technique may have effect on the hostile aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora metropolis.

Research Question 3

What is the effect of values clarification counselling technique on instrumental aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora Metropolis?

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Table 3: Result of Descriptive Statistic of Mean, Standard Deviation on the Effect VC Counselling Technique on Instrumental Aggressive Behaviour among Secondary School Kontagora Metropolis

Treatment	Variables	N	Mean	SD
VCCT	Pre-Test	15	21.67	4.32
	Post-Test	15	8.80	4.80

Table 3 revealed the descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation on the effect of values clarification counselling on instrumental aggressive behaviour among secondary school students in Kontagora metropolis, Nigeria. The table shows pre-test mean score of 21.67 and post-test mean score of 8.80. This implies that the post-test have a mean reduction of 12.87 from the pre-test. This suggests that social skills counselling may have significant effect on relational aggressive behaviour among secondary school students in Kontagora metropolis, Nigeria.

Research Question 4

What is the effect of values clarification counselling technique on relational aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora Metropolis?

Table 4: Result of Descriptive Statistic of Mean, Standard Deviation on the Effect VC Counselling Technique on Relational Aggressive Behaviour among Secondary School Kontagora Metropolis

Treatment	Variables	N	Mean	SD
VCCT	Pre-Test	15	28.27	12.570
	Post-Test	15	21.53	12.956

Table 4 showed the result of descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation on the effect of value clarification counselling technique on relational aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora metropolis, Nigeria. The table shows pre-test mean score of 28.27 and post-test mean score of 21.53. This implies that the post-test have a mean reduction of 6.74 from the pre-test. This suggests that values clarification counselling technique may have significant effect on relational aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora metropolis, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between values clarification counselling and hostility behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora Metropolis.

Table 5: Summary of Paired Sample t-test Statistics on Effect of Values Clarification Counselling Techniques on Hostility Behaviour among Secondary School Students in Kontagora Metropolis

Treatment	Variables	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	p-value
VCCT	Pre-test	15	52.73	5.89	14	11.00	.000
	Post-test	15	24.13	7.75			

*p value < .05

From Table 5, the subjects exposed to values clarification counselling technique had pre-test mean score of 52.73 with standard deviation of 5.89 and post-test mean score of 24.13 with a standard deviation of 7.75. This implies a mean difference of 28.60. This is an indication that students exposed to values clarification counselling treatment achieved a mean reduction in their post test score compared to their pretest which may be attributed to the treatment. At 14 degree of freedom and 11.00 t-values, the p-value was found to be .000 which was less than the chosen alpha of .05 thus, there is statistical significant effect of values clarification counselling technique on hostile aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school student Kontagora metropolis, Nigeria. The null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between values clarification counselling technique and hostile aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora Metropolis, Nigeria was rejected.

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Hypothesis 2

There is no significant effect of values clarification counselling technique on emotional aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora Metropolis.

Table 6: Summary of Paired Sample t-test Statistics on Effect of Values Clarification Counselling Techniques on Emotional Aggressive Behaviour among Secondary School Students in Kontagora Metropolis

Treatment	Variables	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	p-value
VCCT	Pre-test	15	31.07	5.31	14	6.15	.000
	Post-test	15	16.20	7.56			

*p value < .05

Table 6 revealed that the group exposed to values clarification counselling technique achieved high reduction in their post-test mean score when compare with their pre-test mean score. In their pre-test, values clarification counselling group obtained a mean score of 31.07 with a corresponding standard deviation of 5.31 and post-test mean score of 16.20 with a corresponding standard deviation of 7.56, both at 14 degree of freedom and t-value of 6.15. This indicates that there is a mean reduction of 14.87. The difference in the scores could be as a result of the treatment. The obtained p-value of .000 was found to be lesser than .05 Alpha level of significance. This means that there is significant effect of values clarification counselling technique on emotional aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora metropolis, Nigeria. Thus, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between values clarification counselling technique and emotional aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora Metropolis was rejected.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference between value clarification counselling technique and instrumental aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora Metropolis.

Table 7: Summary of Paired Sample t-test Statistics on Effect of Values Clarification Counselling Techniques on Instrumental Aggressive Behaviour among Secondary School Students in Kontagora Metropolis

Treatment	Variables	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	p-value
VCCT	Pre-test	15	21.67	4.32	14	7.54	.000
	Post-test	15	8.80	4.80			

*p value < .05

The result in table 7 showed that before the treatment, the values clarification counselling technique group obtained a mean score of 21.67 with a corresponding standard deviation of 4.32. After the treatment, the group obtained a mean score of 8.80 with a corresponding standard deviation of 4.80. The result indicates the p-value of .000 which was found to be lesser than the Alpha level of .05. This implies that there is significant effect of values clarification counselling technique on instrumental aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora metropolis, Nigeria. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between values clarification counselling technique and instrumental aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora Metropolis, Nigeria was rejected.

Hypothesis 4

There is no significant difference between values clarification counselling technique and relational aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora Metropolis.

Table 8: Summary of Paired Sample t-test Statistics on Effect of Values Clarification Counselling Techniques on Relational Aggressive Behaviour among Secondary School Students in Kontagora Metropolis

Treatment	Variables	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	p-value
VCCT	Pre test	15	28.27	12.57	14	1.30	.214
	Post test	15	21.53	12.96			

*p value > .05

Table 8 showed that the subjects exposed to values clarification counselling technique had a mean score of 28.27 with corresponding standard deviation of 12.56 before the treatment. After the treatment they obtained a mean score of 21.53 and corresponding standard deviation of 12.96. The table also shows the t-value of 1.30 and p-value of .214 at 14 degree of freedom.

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The p-value was found to be greater than the chosen alpha of .05. Since there is no significant difference in the mean score of pre-test and posttest as a result of the treatment, the values clarification counselling technique is ineffective in reducing relational aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school student in Kontagora metropolis, Nigeria. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that, there is no significant effect of values clarification counselling technique on relational aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora metropolis, Nigeria was retained.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that hypotheses one, two and three which considered the effect of the values clarification technique on hostile, emotional and instrumental aggressive behaviour components among senior secondary school students in Kontagora metropolis were rejected. The findings revealed that there is significant difference between value clarification counselling techniques and hostile aggressive behaviour of senior secondary school students in Kontagora metropolis. The treatment given to the participant in the study provides a learning experience which helps them reflect, examine and recollect about their lives, actions and reactions in order to understand clearly their behaviour (what they like/dislike, want to do/don't want to do). The value clarification treatment exposed the participants to understanding behaviours that are hostile and how they are in variance with their adopted values.

The findings revealed that there is significant effect of value clarification counselling techniques on emotional aggressive behaviour of senior secondary school students in Kontagora metropolis. The value counselling exercise administered helps participants in this study respect the feeling and dispositions of others which reduced their emotional aggressive behaviour against others. In the opinion of Gunawan, Gunawan and Huda (2020), respect is an attitude of appreciation, admiration or respect for others which is meant to convey kind feelings. In their study Gunawan et al (2020), the results confirmed that values clarification group counselling was effective in increasing student respect. The exposure of the participants to value clarification counselling exercise increases their feeling of empathy which make them feel what others feel. The result of the study conducted by Gunawan, Wibowo, Purwanto and Sunawan (2019) revealed that values clarification was effective in increasing empathy. This reduces aggressiveness of participants.

The findings of the study also revealed that hypotheses three which considered the effect of the values clarification technique on instrumental aggressive behaviour components among senior secondary school students in Kontagora metropolis were rejected. This implied that values clarification counselling techniques had significant effect on instrumental aggressive behaviour. The reason for the effectiveness of values clarification counselling technique on aggressive behaviour components of hostility, emotional and instrumental may be because some of the values in the treatment focused on values such as peace, love, respect, patience, forgiveness, dignity, hard work and friendship. Students who care for their health and security of their lives and properties would learn to behave less aggressively. According to Benish-Weisman (2015), the relationship between values and social behaviour has been established across many studies including the relationship of values and aggression. The findings of his study found mutual associations between self-transcendence values and aggression across time. Oliha and Audu (2015) maintained that value clarification technique is effective in the treatment of all forms of antisocial behaviour such as truancy Attribution behaviour, aggression, depression, anxiety, unhappiness, low self-concept and low self-esteem. This is in line with the opinion of Kirschenbaum (2013) that values clarification can be used as a remedial counselling tool to help people work on the issues that are currently causing them unhappiness or other difficulties.

The findings of the study revealed that values clarification counselling technique had no significant effect on relational aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students in Kontagora metropolis, Nigeria. The findings of the study did not reveal significant effect of counselling technique of value clarification on the relational aggressive behaviour component among students of secondary school exposed to the treatment. Comparing the mean score of the pre and post test in the result of the paired sample t-test on relational aggression,

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that values clarification counselling technique is effective in reducing hostile, emotional and instrumental aggressive behaviours of senior secondary school students in Kontagora metropolis, Nigeria. However values clarification counselling was ineffective in reducing relational aggressive behaviour among senior secondary school students.

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Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers recommended that:

1. School counsellors and psychologists should employ values clarification counselling technique in helping students reducing hostile, emotional and instrumental aggressive behaviours among them. In general, values clarification counselling techniques should be emphasized to increase pro-social behaviour, inhibit aggressive responses and handle anti-social behaviour in schools.
2. Most behavioural modification techniques are unconsciously used at home and the society. Since the home contributes to the problem of aggressive child, it is therefore, recommended to parents and guardians to make use of values clarification technique of value voting in helping their aggressive children or wards. Children should be encourage to prize, weigh options and due considerations of what they cherished before decision is taken.
3. Seminars, workshops and conferences should be organized for school teachers and other school staff on the use of values clarification techniques of value voting, public interview, value journals and so on in reducing anti-social behaviour among senior secondary school students.

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